

Minimal Invasive Dentistry: A Review

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Abstract

Minimally invasive procedures are the new model in health care. Minimally invasive dentistry acquire philosophy of prevention, remineralisation and minimal intervention for the placement of restoration and replacement of faulty restorations. Minimally Invasive Dentistry (MID) deals with removal of the minimal amount of healthy tissues with least invasive surgical approach. At microscopic level it embraces the art of detecting, diagnosing, intercepting and treating dental caries.

This technique has evolved from an improved understanding of the caries process and the evolution of adhesive and biomimetic restorative materials. MID consider dental caries as an infectious condition rather than an end product of it. Now “extension for prevention” is no longer practiced but has changed to “constriction with conviction.” This paper reviews in brief the concept of minimal intervention in dentistry.

Keywords: ART, Minimal Invasive Dentistry, Cariology, Air abrasion, Chemomechanical caries removal, Remineralisation.

Introduction

Preserving the sound set of natural teeth for each patient should be the purpose of every dentist. Whole method in the field of health is aimed basically at conservation of the human body and its function. Miles Markley, summarized in his statement the central concept in the modern approach to the dentist's role in the treatment of dental caries: that the loss of even a part of a human dentition should be given utmost importance just like “a serious injury,” and that dentistry's goal should be to preserve healthy, natural tooth structure. His words are more pertinent in today's era than when he wrote them almost half a century ago.

Earlier, dentistry's attitude in treating dental caries has been surgical i.e. excavating carious tissue and restoration with suitable material. With time, contemporary dentistry has progress to a minimally invasive approach, in which caries is managed as an infectious disease, deferring operative intervention as long as possible. The prime target is maximum conservation of demineralized, noncavitated enamel and dentin. Minimally invasive dentistry acquire philosophy of prevention, remineralisation and minimal intervention for the placement of restoration and replacement of faulty restorations. MID expresses very precise excision of what has to be excavated, without causing any damage to adjacent healthy tissue.^[1]

Historical background

Evidence shows that ancient culture used trephines, drills, files, and other suitable devices to prepare ornamental cavities in teeth for beauty purpose. In early 17th century, hand-operated instruments having rotating drill were used to make ornamental cavities in decayed teeth.

G.V. Black was the first dentist to propose treating dental caries using minimal intervention in 1800's. Till that time clinical symptoms were addressed by tooth extraction or restoration. Restorations of that time used an alloy that corroded rapidly and later expand. Buonocore In 1955, described a new approach for etching enamel surfaces to make them retentive for a restoration. In 1960's, the researchers dedicated their expertise in better understanding dental caries and assumption of its relationship to fluoride.^[2] Bowen in 1962 invented an adhesive materials, which lead to the invention of minimal invasive prevention.

Use of silver diamine fluoride (SDF) as a minimal invasive approach in dentistry was early in 1970s. Soon after, many more innovative procedures came forth with the objective of caries prevention. At around 1980, a new technique of preventive resin restoration (PRR) was developed, which was followed by introduction of a traumatic restorative treatment (ART) in 1980s. Different chemo-mechanical caries removal concepts were also introduced in the 1990s. In 1997, it was believed that assessment of carious lesion development and progression played a vital part in provision of adequate oral health.

The first International Association for Dental Research (IADR) symposium on minimal intervention techniques for dental caries was organised at 73rd IADR congress in Singapore in 1995 and was almost entirely focused on Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART). Which was one of the minimal invasive approach.^[3]

Objectives of MID

Minimally invasive dentistry requires a change in approach to managing dental caries. Dental caries needs to be considered as a bacterial disease rather than the end product of that disease. The prime objectives of MID helps in suppressing the bacteria, limiting the substrate upon which they survive and its duration in the mouth, enhancing the oral environment (increasing saliva and its minerals), and protecting the teeth with fluoride and sealants in addition to the usual oral hygiene methods.

Following are the objectives of minimal invasive dentistry

1. Identification of disease causing factors by evaluation of saliva, which includes salivary flow rate, salivary pH, concentration of bicarbonates in saliva and its viscosity⁽⁴⁾. Evaluation of caries activity with the help of various caries activity test⁽⁵⁾. Assessing occlusion and other tooth factors such as heredity pattern, systemic condition like xerostomia and vitamin or protein deficiency. Understanding patient environment like their socioeconomic condition, education level, monthly income as all these factors are associated with the prevalence of dental caries. Frequency of diet and the type of diet are associated with caries progression hence analysing patients diet with the help of diet chart followed by diet counselling is necessary.
2. Prevention of disease by combating caries inducing microorganism with the help of Bisguanides (chlorhexidine) and triclosan. Modifying caries promoting ingredients & use of sugar substitutes (Xylitol). Increasing resistance of teeth to decay with the help of topical fluoride, pit and fissure sealant and remineralising agents such as amorphous calcium phosphate.
3. Control of disease by either reducing the attacking forces such as removing dental plaque, altering the plaque microflora and by reducing dietary sugar to reduce acid production or enhancing the host resistance by use of preventive fluoride application and by using various remineralizing agents.

Principles of MID

The core principles of minimal invasive dentistry are as follow:-

- Early detection of lesion and disease control through reduction of cariogenic flora.
- Remineralization of early lesions.
- Minimal surgical intervention of caries lesions.
- Repair of faulty restoration rather than a replacement.
- Examining restorations.

Basic approaches to minimal invasive dentistry

Use of Fluoride for Preventing Dental Caries

The discovery of fluoride in dentistry (1901) has revolutionized treatment modalities with a new aspect of prevention and conservation of tooth structure coming into foreplay. Since then, there has been a lot of research on both topical and systemic fluoridation in an overzealous attempt to control the most debilitating dental problem of caries. Various forms of fluoride are available which are classified as self-applied and professionally applied. Self-applied topical fluorides include toothpastes, mouth rinses, and gels. Professionally applied topical fluorides include higher-strength rinses, gels, and foams; fluoride varnishes; and silver diamine fluoride.

Although topical fluoride is still being widely used as a preventive measure for dental caries, systemic administration of the same has gained major criticism worldwide due to the low margin of safety of fluoride and no control over the amount of individual intake when administered on a community level.

Application of Silver Diamine Fluoride

Silver diamine fluoride (SDF) was first investigated as a part of Mizuho Nishino, phd's thesis at Osaka University in Japan in 1969. It is a colourless, clear liquid that combine both the antibacterial effects of silver and the remineralizing property of fluoride ion, it is a promising therapeutic agent for managing carious lesions in young children and in those with special care needs. Various in vitro studies has shown its effectiveness in reducing specific cariogenic bacteria.⁽⁶⁾

The fluoride component provide strength to the tooth structure for attack by the acid byproduct of microbial metabolism, reducing its solubility and interfere with the biofilm. killing bacteria which are responsible for local environmental imbalance that demineralizes dental tissues.⁽⁷⁾ The only apparent drawback is that as the caries lesions become arrested, the precipitation of silver byproducts in the dental tissues stain the lesions black, which is unaesthetic in visible areas.⁽⁸⁾

Preventive Resin Restoration (PRR)

With the advent of newer restorative materials the ideology of sealing for prevention of fissure caries came into practice. Due to superior wear resistance and mechanical properties, composite resin materials are the material of choice rather than glass ionomer for the treatment of early occlusal caries in permanent teeth. PRR is the invasive and noninvasive treatment of borderline or questionable caries. PRRs were first described by Simonsen and Stallard in 1977.⁽⁹⁾ The resin placed in the carious areas and adjacent caries susceptible areas, seals them from the oral environment.

Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART)

Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART) was initially developed as a new treatment method for carious restoration in developing countries where definitive treatment is difficult due to lack of resources. The ART was started way back in Tanzania in the mid 1980s which was then followed by several community field trials conducted in Thailand and Zimbabwe in 1991 and 1993 respectively. The American Academy of Paediatric Dentistry (AAPD) defines ART as "a dental caries treatment procedure involving the removal of soft, demineralized tooth tissue using hand instrument alone, followed by adhesive restorative material, which is routinely glass ionomer cement".⁽¹⁰⁾

The fluoride ion released from the GIC initiate the fluorapatite crystal formation, which is more acid-resistant, making the tooth less vulnerable to caries. GIC can be recharged and may acts as a reservoir of fluoride ions taken up from topical fluoride applications. Recently, the use of SDF with ART has been initiated known as Silver Modified Atraumatic Restorative Technique (SMART). Drawback associated with ART include lack of its wear resistance, marginal gaps, and loss of restorations. Many attempts have been made to refine the effectiveness of ART with the addition of antimicrobial agents. CHX was added to GIC which reduce the number of residual bacteria remaining in the cavity after the removal of infected tissue. Various research and meta analyses shown that Success rates for ART restorations depend on the material used, training of the operator, and extent of caries.⁽¹¹⁻¹⁴⁾

Pit and Fissure Sealants

Protecting the natural pits and fissures of newly erupted teeth from dental decay is not a new concept. There have been numerous references to reducing the decay susceptibility of pits and fissures since 1923 when H. T. Hyatt suggested a technique called prophylactic odontotomy. In 1983 the National Institutes of Health published a report entitled, "Consensus Development Conference Statement on Dental Sealants in the Prevention of Tooth Decay." This report recommended the use of pit and fissure sealants as a safe and effective method of preventing pit and fissure decay.

Sandwich technique

In this technique composite resin is bonded over GIC. It is mainly done in conditions where occlusal load is more and there is lack of enamel to provide adhesion to composite resin. It takes advantage of strong adhesion of GIC to tooth structure and superior physical properties of resin-based composite.

It involves placement of Resin Modified Glass Ionomer Cement (RMGI) at the base of the prepared cavity, followed by curing and the addition of composite restoratives to complete the restoration. Mainly there are two type of sandwich technique i.e. closed sandwich technique (If the remaining layers of composite resin completely encase the RMGI), open sandwich technique (If the RMGI is exposed to the oral environment at the base of the restoration).

The sandwich technique has been introduced since 40 years, It is commonly practiced among permanent teeth; however, there are very few studies done on use of sandwich technique in primary teeth.⁽¹⁵⁾ A study done by Cannon ML in 2003 for evaluation of the clinical efficacy of the open sandwich technique in pediatric dental practice concluded that open sandwich technique can be successfully practiced in primary teeth.⁽¹⁶⁾

Hall technique

Another minimally invasive restoration therapy introduced especially for deciduous teeth that may be helpful in reducing the treatment burden of cavitated carious lesions in dentine is the Hall technique. The Hall technique is one of the methods for sealing in caries in primary molars.⁽¹⁷⁾ The Hall technique using preformed metal crowns (PMCs) was pioneered in the literature in 2006 by Scottish Dr. Norna Hall.

In this technique, the crown is placed without caries removal, or tooth preparation and without giving local anesthesia. Instead an appropriate size of PMC is selected and filled with glass ionomer cement. The crown is then fitted over the carious primary molar using finger pressure, or by simply asking child to bite over it.⁽¹⁸⁾

The Hall technique has very straightforward biological principles. It protect the primary tooth until shedding by arresting carious progression. Mechanism behind Hall technique is that the superficial plaque layer is left and sealed along with carious lesion, which is the most essential layer in the biofilm for caries progression. As a response, the plaque biofilm composition will be shifted to a less cariogenic microflora, which in turn arrest or slows down the caries progression in primary teeth.⁽¹⁹⁾

Chemico-mechanical caries excavation

The procedure involves application of chemical agent on carious dentin, which acts on pre-degraded collagen fibres of outer infected and non remineralizable dentin and promotes its softening. Subsequently, soft carious tissue is removed by gentle excavation (mechanical action) without affecting the healthy tissues. Various chemomechanical caries removal systems are used like: Caridex, Carisolv, Papacarie and CarieCare. They are sodium hypochlorite-based or Papain enzyme based agents.

Ozone Therapy

Ozone is a powerful oxidizer which effectively kills bacteria, fungi, viruses and parasites at very low concentration. It readily penetrates through decayed dental tissue, eliminating the ecological niche of cariogenic microorganisms and breaks up the acidic products of cariogenic bacteria. It is expected that 'clean' lesion can remineralize with aid of topically applied remineralizing agents. Once ozone treatment of the carious lesion is completed a remineraling solution containing 2% sodium fluoride and 5% xylitol is applied to promote healing of the caries lesion.⁽²⁰⁾ This simple and fast approach avoids the need for administration of local anaesthesia, drilling and filling, however, its application is restricted to treat superficial enamel lesions and root caries only.

Resin Infiltration Technique

Resin infiltration or caries infiltration is an innovative approach primarily to arrest the progression of non-cavitated white spot lesions, non-cavitated interproximal caries lesions, or incipient proximal lesions, with a light curable resin.^(21, 22) The infiltrating resin not require any shade matching due to its high refractive index which produces a chameleon effect. It works on capillary action; a low viscosity resin is drawn deep into lesion. The resin fills the pores system and block further passage of nutrient into pores within the tooth, which ultimately block the carious progression. Also it maintain the anatomical shape of tooth by replacing lost tooth structure. The lesions change their optical properties and appear similar to sound enamel.

MID in Pediatric Dentistry

MID approach to keep the teeth functional throughout the life and it is applicable to every dental specialty, particularly in paediatric dentistry. It is difficult to provide oral care to a young patient while ignoring the concepts of MID. Besides all the benefits in terms of tooth tissue preservation, MID is considered a friendly approach, which reduces patient anxiety and offer health-oriented treatment options.

The implementation of topical fluoride therapies like fluoride varnish, fluoride gel and fluoridated mouth rinses – in combination with fluoridated toothpaste was shown to have an added caries reduction effect. A personalised treatment plan, considering the child Caries Risk Assessment (CRA), will assist the professional in deciding whether and which of these therapies are needed.

Recent Advancement in MID

The preventive aspect includes numerous remineralizing agents, such as fluorides, xylitol, nanohydroxyapatite, and other calcium and phosphate based remineralizing agents; however, in order to achieve a biomimetic remineralization, use of remineralizing agents such as calciumphosphate and Bioactive Glass appear in the preventive field.

Casein phosphopeptide– amorphous calcium phosphate complex (CPP-ACP) is a calcium phosphate complex made up of casein phosphopeptide and amorphous calcium phosphate. CPP casein has the unique ability to adapt to an acid-base environment. At an acidic Ph, this ACP get separates from CPP, which result in increased calcium and phosphate levels in saliva which maintenance the state of supersaturation. The CPP-ACP complexes have been shown to prevent demineralization and enhance remineralization in the presence of fluoride.⁽²³⁾

Glycine- guided remineralization mimics the natural biomineralization process, which results in the formation of well-oriented rod-like hydroxyapatite crystals that restore the mechanical properties of demineralized enamel.

Novamin's chemical name is calcium sodium phosphosilicate. It's a bioactive glass which is made up of minerals which are present in the human body. It responds when comes into contact with saliva, water, or other bodily fluids. This formula is used in varnish, toothpaste, and root desensitizer products, and it is available in varnish, toothpaste, and root desensitizer form.⁽²⁴⁾

Tri calcium phosphate (TCP) has the chemical formula $\text{Ca}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2$ and comes in alpha and beta forms. In an aqueous oral setting, it is relatively insoluble. The organic coating prevents fluoride interactions, but it dissolves as particles come into contact with saliva.

Smartburs®- These are the polymer burs which when approaches the sound dentin, they self-limit, hence they retain the sound tooth structure. That's why they are also referred to as "dentin protected." For selective dentine caries elimination, smart-prep polymer burs are a relatively new and naval launch.

Sonicflex system- The sonic oscillating, SONIC flex system (KaVo Dental) was developed to finish mild to moderate proximal cavities. This system uses highly frequent oscillating preparation instruments in an air-driven oscillating hand piece (Airscaler, SONICflex 2003, KaVo Dental). It minimize the damage to neighbouring teeth during proximal preparation and finishing.

Air abrasion excavation (kinetic system)- Air abrasion is also referred to as advanced particle beam/or micro-abrasive technology. Kinetic cavity preparation (KCP) is a technique, which uses fine particles of powder fired at high speed in a controlled manner instead of the traditional high and low speed drills. Quantity of tooth removal and depth of penetration depends on air pressure, particle size, and nozzle diameter of the hand piece, distance and time of exposure to the object.⁽²⁵⁾

Dental caries vaccine- Vaccines are immunobiological substances which are designed to develop specific protection against any given disease.⁽²⁶⁾ vaccines act by stimulation for the production of a protective antibody and other immune mechanisms. Vaccines are mainly prepared either from live-modified organisms, nonvital organism, cellular extract, toxoids, or by fusion of these substances. Caries vaccine are specially designed to play protective part against dental caries. Its very well known that *S. mutans* is main culprit behind pathogenesis of tooth decay.⁽²⁷⁾ Similar to any other vaccine, caries vaccine should also be administered before the introduction of the infectious agent into the system. Hosts when immunized with *S. mutans* antigen, in response to it antibodies are formed within saliva which induce antigen-antibody reaction by cellular aggregation. These cellular aggregates minimizes the number of organisms adhering to the tooth surfaces.

Very few studies have analyzed the efficacy of active immunity against *mutans streptococci* in humans. Most of the authors verified the efficacy of oral administration. Mestecky et al. demonstrated that ingestion of capsules that contained *Streptococcus sobrinus* and this effectively induced sIgA in the saliva.⁽²⁸⁾ Contradicting to these findings, Gahnberg and Krasse when orally administered heat-killed *S. sobrinus* cells given to six subjects, resulting in no salivary IgA response.⁽²⁹⁾ Oral immunization in seven subjects with an enteric coated capsule containing 500 µg of GTF from *S. mutans* resulted in elevated salivary IgA antibodies to the antigen preparation. When similar antigen was administered intranasally or by topical application to tonsils, it resulted in increase of salivary IgA antibodies.^(30,31)

Conclusion

“The preservation of what remains is of utmost importance than the meticulous replacement of that which has been lost.” It is not possible to imitate natural tooth structure on a long term basis, so it is best that it should be retained as far as possible

To preserve healthy tooth structure, minimally invasive procedures and materials should be used because the carious process cannot be reversed. Newer treatment approaches allow us to preserve as much of the sound tooth structure as possible during caries removal. While further research is required, currently it can be concluded that Minimum Intervention has the potential to provide a more conservative approach to caries treatment as well as a health-oriented treatment choice. The ultimate aim of MID approach is to make a transition from “Extension for Prevention” to “Prevention of extension”.

References

- Murdoch-Kinch CA, McLean MA. Minimally invasive dentistry. *Journal of American Dental Association*. 2004; 134: 87-95.
- Bhatiya P, Thosar N. Minimal invasive dentistry-An emerging trend in pediatric dentistry: A review. *International Journal of Contemporary. Dental and Medical Review*. 2015;1-6.
- Horowitz AM. Introduction to the symposium on minimal intervention techniques for caries. *J Public Health Dent*. 1996; 56:133-134.
- Fenoll-Palomares C, Munoz-Montagud JV, Sanchiz V, Herreros B, Hernandez V, Minguez M, Benages A. Unstimulated salivary flow rate, pH, & buffer capacity of saliva in healthy volunteers. *Rev Esp Enferm Dig* 2004;96:773-83
- Peter S. Caries activity test. 3rd ed. New Delhi: Arya (Medi) Publishing House. 1000:359-67.
- Mei ML, Li QL, Chu CH, et al. Antibacterial effects of silver diamine fluoride on multi-species cariogenic biofilm on caries. *Ann Clin Microbiol Antimicrob* 2013; 12:4.
- Mei ML, Nudelman F, Marzec B, et al. Formation of fluorohydroxyapatite with silver diamine fluoride. *J Dent Res* 2017;96(10):1122-8.
- Roberts A, Bradley J, Merkley S, et al. Does potassium iodide application following silver diamine fluoride reduce staining of tooth? A systematic review. *Aust Dent J* 2020;65(2):109-17.
- Simonsen RJ, Stallard RE. Sealant-restorations utilizing a diluted filled composite resin: one year results. *Quintessence Int Dent Dig*. 1977 Jun;8(6):77-84.
- Peter S. Essentials of public health dentistry. 6th ed. New delhi: Arya Medi Publishing House Pvt. Ltd. 2017
- Van't Hof MA, Frencken JE, van Palenstein Helderma WH, Holmgren CJ. The Atraumatic Restorative Treatment (ART) approach for managing dental caries: a meta-analysis. *Int Dent J*. 2006;56:345-51.
- Frencken JE, Makoni F, Sithole WD, Hackenitz E. Three-year survival of one-surface ART restorations and glass-ionomer sealants in a school oral health programme in Zimbabwe. *Caries Res*. 1998;32(2):119-26.
- Frencken JE, Van 't Hof MA, Van Amerongen WE, Holmgren CJ. Effectiveness of single-surface ART restorations in the permanent dentition: a meta-analysis. *J Dent Res*. 2004 Feb;83(2).
- Ersin NK, Candan U, Akyut A, Oncag O, Eronat C, Kose T. A clinical evaluation of resin-based composite and glass ionomer cement restorations placed in primary teeth using ART approach. *J Am Dent Assoc*. 2006;137:1529-36.
- Kadhi, H & Winnier, J. Sandwich Technique in Primary Teeth: A Review. *Journal of Research in Dental and Maxillofacial Sciences*. 2022;7:267-272.
- M.L. Cannon, “A clinical study of the "open sandwich" technique in pediatric dental practice,” *J Dent Child (Chic)*. Jan 2003. 70(1):65-70.
- Innes NP, EvansDJ, StirrupsDR. Sealing caries in primary molars: Randomized controlled trial—5-year results. *J. Dent. Res*. 2011;90:1405-1410.
- InnesNP, StirrupsDR, EvansDJ, HallN, Leggate M.A novel technique using preformed metal crowns for managing carious primary molars in general practice: A retrospective analysis. *Br. Dent. J*. 2006;200:451-454.
- Kidd, EA. How 'clean' must a cavity be before restoration? *Caries Res*. 2004;38:305-313.
- Domb WC. Ozone therapy in dentistry. A brief review for physicians. *Interv Neuroradiol*. 2014;20(5):632-636.
- Kugel G, Arsenault Pet al. Treatment modalities for caries management, including a new resin infiltration system. *Compend Contin Educ Dent*. 2009 Oct;30(3):1-10
- Arslan S, Zorba YO et al. Effect of resin infiltration on enamel surface properties and Streptococcus mutans adhesion to artificial enamel lesions. *Dent Mater J*. 2015 Jan;34(1):25-30.
- Llena C, Forner L, Baca P. Anticariogenicity of casein phosphopeptide-amorphous calcium phosphate: a review of the literature. *J Contemp Dent Pract*. 2009 May 1;10(3):1-9.
- Showkat N, Singh G, Singla K, Sareen K, Chowdhury C, Jindal L. Minimal Invasive Dentistry: Literature Review. *Journal of Current Medical Research and Opinion*. 2020;3(09):631-6
- Hegde VS, Khatavkar RA. A new dimension to conservative dentistry: Air abrasion. *J Conserv Dent*. 2010 Jan;13(1):4-8.
- Krithika AC, Kandaswamy D, Gopikrishna V. Caries vaccine-I today's myth. *J Indian Assoc Public Health Dent* 2004;4:21-5.
- Cherukuri G, Veeramachaneni C, Rao GV, Pacha VB, Balla SB. Insight into status of dental caries vaccination: A review. *J Conserv Dent*. 2020;23(6):544-549.
- Mestecky J, McGhee JR, Arnold RR, Michalek SM, Prince SJ, Babb JL, et al. Selective induction of an immune response in human external secretions by ingestion of bacterial antigen. *J Clin Invest* 1978;61:731-7.
- Gahnberg L, Krasse B. Salivary immunoglobulin A antibodies and recovery from challenge of Streptococcus mutans after oral administration of Streptococcus mutans vaccine in humans. *Infect Immun* 1983;39:514-9.
- Childers NK, Zhang SS, Michalek SM. Oral immunization of humans with dehydrated liposomes containing Streptococcus mutans glucosyltransferase induces salivary immunoglobulin A2 antibody responses. *Oral Microbiol Immunol* 1994;9:146-53.
- Childers NK, Tong G, Li F, Dasanayake AP, Kirk K, Michalek SM, et al. Humans immunized with Streptococcus mutans antigens by mucosal routes. *J Dent Res* 2002;81:48-52.